

Cyclopentadienyltitanium (IV) Chelates*

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Direct substitution of chlorine atoms in bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) dichloride by some chelate groups is under study. Reactions between bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) dichloride and 8-quinolinol, acetoacetanilide and dibenzoylmethane give respectively bis(8-quinolinolato) cyclopentadienyltitanium(IV) chloride, acetoacetanilidato bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) chloride and 1,3-Diphenyl-1,3-propanedianatobis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) chloride. The infrared spectra of these compounds have been discussed.

Although a number of cyclopentadienyltitanium compounds with various ligands besides the cyclopentadienyl groups have been reported¹⁻⁵, those containing a chelated ligand are rather few. Nesmeyanov *et al.*⁶, reported the first compound of this type, containing 8-quinolinolato group. The only other work to report this class of compounds is the recent synthesis³ of β -diketonate chelates of bis(cyclopentadienyl) titanium moiety $[(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{TiL}^+]\text{X}^-$ where L is the conjugate base of acetylacetone, benzoylacetone, dibenzoylmethane, dipivaloylmethane and tropolone, and X^- may be ClO_4^- , BF_4^- , PF_6^- , AsF_6^- , SbF_6^- or F_3CSO_3^- . Since no direct substitution of chlorine atoms in bis(cyclopentadienyl) titanium dichloride, $(\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{TiCl}_2$, by a chelate group has been reported, it was of interest to study these reactions with various ligands containing donor atoms. Recently, dithiolate compounds such as bis(cyclopentadienyl)maleonitriledithiolato titanium (IV) have been synthesized^{4,5}, but in these compounds the titanium (IV) is still four coordinate.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the organic ligands were of pure quality or purified where necessary. Solvents were purified by standard procedures. BDH analytical reagents were used in analytical determinations.

Titanium was determined by fuming the compounds with conc. sulphuric and nitric acids, precipitating the metal with cupferron and igniting to oxide. For chloride determination, the compounds were fused with sodium carbonate, the melt dissolved in water and the solution was titrated by Volhard's method. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were determined microanalytically.

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2. S. A. Giddings, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **6**, 849.
3. R. S. Tobias and G. Doyle, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **6**, 1111.
4. J. A. McCleverty and J. Locke, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 1157.
5. M. Schmidt and H. Köpf, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 426.
6. A. N. Nesmeyanov and O. V. Nogina, *Izv. Akad. Nauk. SSSR, Otd. Khim. Nauk*, 1963, 831-5.

Infrared spectra of the compounds in Nujol mull were recorded in the NaCl optics region by means of Perkin-Elmer Infracord Model 137-B.

Bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium dichloride was prepared by the known methods^{7,8}. Recrystallization from toluene gave bright red crystals of the compound, whose purity was checked by melting point and elemental analysis.

Bis(8-quinolinalato)cyclopentadienyttitanium (IV) chloride : To a solution of 1.425 g. (0.0098 mole) of 8-quinolinal in 80 ml. of benzene, 1.13 g. (0.00454 mole) of bis(cyclopentadienyl) titanium dichloride was added and the mixture heated under reflux when a clear coloured solution was obtained. Heating under reflux was continued for 150 hr till evolution of HCl ceased. On cooling overnight and filtering, a red coloured filtrate and brown residue were obtained. The brown residue was treated thrice at the reflux temperature with benzene (40 ml. each time) and the benzene extracts mixed with the filtrate. On concentrating the solution (1/3 volume) by distilling off the solvent under reduced pressure and standing overnight, a red coloured solid was obtained. This was collected on a frit, washed several times with small quantities of benzene and petroleum ether (B.R. 63–65°), and dried under vacuum. Yield 37%. Found : C, 62.61; H, 3.93; N, 6.63; Ti, 11.75; Cl, 8.50. Calcd. for $C_{23}H_{17}O_2N_2TiCl$: C, 63.23; H, 3.89; N, 6.41; Ti, 11.02; Cl, 8.13%.

The compound is moderately soluble in benzene and chloroform.

Infrared absorption maxima (in cm^{-1}) of the compound are given below :

2950(vs)*, 2865(sh), 2700(m,br.), 1690(m), 1580(m), 1497(s), 1470(vs)*, 1430(sh), 1380(vs)*, 1325(s), 1275(s), 1227(w), 1175(w), 1105(s), 1075(sh), 1053(vw), 1025(m), 1015(sh), 910(vw), 855(sh), 840(sh), 835(sh), 827(s), 810(m), 790(m), 745(s).

*Nujol peak; vs = very strong; s = strong; m = medium; vw = very weak; w = weak; sh = shoulder.

Acetoacetanilidatobis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium (IV) chloride : To a solution of 1.86 g. (0.0105 mole) acetoacetanilide in 80 ml. of benzene, 1.312 g. (0.0053 mole) of bis(cyclopentadienyl) titanium dichloride was added and the mixture heated under reflux. A clear solution was obtained after sometime and heating under reflux was continued for nearly 300 hr till evolution of HCl ceased. A red coloured substance was found to have been deposited on the sides of the reaction flask. On cooling and filtering, a red coloured solid and a red coloured filtrate were obtained. The filtrate was concentrated and the crystals obtained on cooling were found to be unreacted bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium dichloride. The solid was heated with 60 ml. of benzene to the reflux temperature for 3 hr, filtered when cooled, washed several times with small quantities of benzene and petroleum ether (B.R. 63–65°), and dried under vacuum. Yield 20%; m.p. 239–240° with decomposition. Found :

7. G. Wilkinson and J. M. Birmingham, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 4281.

8. J. M. Birmingham, cited in *Advances in Organometallic Chemistry*, Vol. 2, edited by F. G. A. Stone and R. West (Academic Press, New York), 1964, 373.

C, 61.56; H, 4.88; N, 4.06; Ti, 12.77; Cl, 9.71. Calcd. for $C_{20}H_{10}O_2NTiCl$: C, 61.61; H, 5.13;

The compound is very slightly soluble in benzene and insoluble in chloroform.

Infrared absorption maxima (cm^{-1}) of the compound are given below :

3250(m), 3150(w), 2900(vs)*, 1650(s), 1600(s), 1575(s), 1590(s), 1500(sh), 1460(s)*, 1410(s), 1385(m)*, 1335(m), 1320(s), 1300(sh), 1260(s), 1195(s), 1160(w), 1080(w), 1050(s), 1035(m), 1008(w), 978(vs), 908(w), 840(m), 830(s), 790(m), 760(s), 742(w), 690(m).

1,3-Diphenyl-1,3-propanediantobis(cyclopentadienyl) titanium (IV) chloride : To a solution of 2.675 g. dibenzoylmethane (0.0120 mole) in 80 ml. of benzene, 1.49 g. (0.0060 mole) of bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium dichloride was added and the mixture heated under reflux to give a clear solution. Heating under reflux was continued for about 380 hr. till HCl evolution ceased. The red solution turned dark brown in colour and then a deep orange coloured solid was collected on the sides of the reaction flask. The solid was collected on a frit, washed several times with small quantities of benzene and petroleum ether (B.R. 63–65°), and dried under vacuum. Yield 22%. Found : C, 68.61; H, 4.47; Ti, 10.35; Cl, 7.57. Calcd. for $C_{25}H_{21}O_2TiCl$: C, 68.72; H, 4.81; Ti, 10.99; Cl, 8.12%.

The compound is very slightly soluble in benzene and chloroform.

The filtrate from the deep orange solid on concentration gave red crystals which were identified as unreacted bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium dichloride.

Infrared absorption maxima (in cm^{-1}) of the compound are given below :

2900(vs)*, 1600(m), 1560(s), 1545(s), 1525(s), 1485(sh), 1470(vs)*, 1450(sh), 1415(sh), 1380(m)*, 1350(m), 1320(s), 1300(s), 1230(m), 1185(m), 1165(m), 1125(w), 1075(m), 1030(m), 1005(w), 947(w), 895(vw), 852(w), 820(m), 770(s,br), 758(s,sh), 715(m), 683(m).

DISCUSSION

The reaction between bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium dichloride and 8-quinolinol may be represented by the equation :

Cyclopentadiene was detected in the reaction mixture. An analogous product was obtained by Nesmeyanov *et al.*⁶, by an indirect route, by first obtaining a similar ethoxy compound, $C_5H_5Ti(OEt)(ONC_9H_6)_2$, by reacting cyclopentadienyl-triethoxytitanium, $C_5H_5Ti(OEt)_3$ with 8-quinolinol, and subsequently reacting this compound with acetyl chloride.

The reactions with acetoacetanilide and dibenzoylmethane may be written as :

Characteristic of all 8-quinolinol chelates⁹, a strong band at 1105 cm^{-1} due to the C-O stretching frequency at C-O-M site is observed for the bis(8-quinolinolato) cyclopentadienyl-titanium chloride. The bands at 1580 cm^{-1} (C = N str.), 1275 cm^{-1} (benzene and pyridine ring vibrations) are characteristic vibrations of the 8-quinolinol¹⁰. The strong band at 827 cm^{-1} (C-H out of plane bending)^{5,11} shoulders at 1015 cm^{-1} (C-H in plane bending)^{3,11} and 1430 cm^{-1} (π -C₅H₅ ring str.)^{3,11} can be assigned to the cyclopentadienyl group.

The chelation of the acetoacetanilide ligand to the metal is evidenced by the absence of the strong carbonyl absorption band of the ligand at 1727 cm^{-1} and the presence of a strong band of chelated carbonyl¹² at 1575 cm^{-1} . It is of interest to note in this spectrum as also in those reported by Sen and Umapathy¹², that the strong band at 1080 cm^{-1} of the ligand becomes weak in the acetoacetanilidato chelates with the appearance of a strong band in the proximity of 1050 cm^{-1} . The amide bands in the chelate can be located at 1600 cm^{-1} (amide I + C = C), 1540 cm^{-1} (amide II), 1300 cm^{-1} (amide III) and the N-H str. band at 3250 cm^{-1} . The strong band at 830 cm^{-1} (C-H out of plane bending) and a weak band at 1008 cm^{-1} (C-H in plane bending), a medium band at 1410 cm^{-1} (π -C₅H₅ ring str.) and a shoulder at 3075 cm^{-1} (C-H str.) are due to cyclopentadienyl rings.

9. R. G. Charles, H. Freiser, R. Friedel, L. E. Hillard and W. D. Johnston, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1956, **8**, 1.

10. D. N. Sen and P. Umapathy, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, (in press).

11. H. P. Fritz, cited in *Advances in Organometallic Chemistry*, Vol. 1, edited by F. G. A. Stone and R. West (Academic Press, New York), 1964, 262-290.

12. D. N. Sen and P. Umapathy, *Indian J. Chem.* (in press).

In the spectra of the metal complexes of the β -diketones, acetylacetone and dibenzoylmethane, the C = C stretching mode occurs at 1600–1570 cm^{-1} and the C = O stretch^{13,14} at 1590–1530 cm^{-1} . Accordingly, the bands observed at 1600 cm^{-1} and 1560 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of compound with dibenzoylmethane may be assigned respectively to C = C stretch and C = O stretch. The bands at 820 cm^{-1} , 1030 cm^{-1} , 1450 cm^{-1} can be attributed to the cyclopentadienyl groups.

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